

INVESTIGATING THE EFFECTS OF OVER TOURISM ON DESTINATION SUSTAINABILITY: A GLOBAL CASE STUDY

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1. Abstract

Over tourism has a significant impact on tourism industry and improvement of the destination. And issues caused by overcrowding are major problem for the most popular and most visited countries nowadays. This research explores the effects of overcrowding on sustainability of destination in the globe.

In this study quantitative data method, with different kind of Literature reviews from reliable sources such as Google scholar, research Gate, Scopus and others were used to analyze how tourism congestion influence on tourism industry. By examining data about several countries around the world, such as, Amsterdam, Italy and Greece which faced to over tourism and this research gives some recommendations for developing the quality of sustainable travel services and some ways to avoid over tourism.

Key words: Over tourism, Sustainability, Travel services, Amsterdam, Italy, Greece

2. Introduction

Over tourism has a strong negative impact on the quality of life of people and guests' experiences in a destination. The growth of tourism is depending on many factors, such as tourists flow into a destination, environmental sustainability of a country, political stability and others.

Firstly, overcrowding can cause to lack of accommodation facilities and lack of resources, besides that it can damage the environment because of wasting many resources or products in that destination. And the main reasons of tourism congestion in tourists' destinations can be the number of increasing social media advertisements and not to promote small cities and country sides of those places.

Mobility is the first reason because nowadays it is impossible do not find popular tourist destinations on social media and it can lead many visitors to these countries. And the second one is promoting only city centers to attract many visitors with improving the quality of tourism products, while not promoting urban places. That is why most of popular city centers are so busy

with people. And all of these reasons led to cultural erosion and social disruption.

As a consequence of visiting many tourists in a destination, it can lead the damaging of natural ecosystems, and it will be one of the serious issues for future sustainability. By analyzing the impacts of this problem among the most developed countries around the world, this research aims to explain what kind of actions and ways, government can take for keeping their tourism industry stable.

2.1 Objectives of the research

The objectives of study are followings:

1. To examine how over tourism effects on tourism industry in a global scale.
2. To analyze several steps and strategies to reduce the negative influences of overcrowding in developed countries.
3. To focus on understanding environmental and economic impacts of over tourism.
4. To give some recommendations and suggestions to improve the quality of tourism sustainability.

2.2 Literature review

According to the scholar Goodwin (2017:1), over tourism is “both visitors and local residents feel that there are so many visitors and it influence its effect on quality of guests’ experience and local people’s life”. It can lead to crowdedness and lack of capacity in a specific tourism destination. Without doubt, tourism is one of the main aspects to understand cultural exchanges and help to understand cross-cultural communications, but sometimes it shows its detrimental implications in social life of residents, pollution, cultural deterioration, and increasing the cost of living in a specific area (Roberts, Renda & Pinto, 2022).

Besides that, it is very crucial to improve the skill of government policies and to design management equipment for minimizing the negative effects before its influence (Gonza-lez Reverte,2022). One of the main problems with overcrowding can lead to increase the cost of living which is negatively related to the individuals’ quality of life. According to the many researchers of this field, it is highlighted that, many countries will come across to this problem in next years (Butter,2018).

Although excessive tourism has detrimental impacts, however, it also has positive effects on local tourism. It can give them several economic opportunities (Annar et. al, 2019). Haspers (2019) said that, tourism industry

plays a crucial role in Europe, because of its assistance on economy growth, however, it has both adverse social and physical consequences.

3. Approach

This study collects the information from the reliable sources according to the previous literature reviews such as Google Scholar, Scopus, Research Gate and etc. Data collection method includes analysis of secondary sources such as reports and country documents about tourist arrivals in the most visited destinations around the world. The study focuses on to connect with the environmental, social, economic effects of overcrowding in these developed countries and it explores the strategies, tactics and ways which government try to reduce the mass tourism.

4. Outcomes

- This research explored that over tourism has negative effects on improvement of different factors of destination. Such as, it influences culture of state, social life, natural environment, quality of life and etc.
- The research highlighted that, it is very important to protect the cultural heritages, natural areas, to promote sustainable tourism, eco-tourism, and country sides for improving their tourism industry as city centers.
- Besides that, it is also crucial that to bring the community, government, stakeholders, tour operators or others to protect both cultural and environmental sites of a country. Because, they help to reduce the negative effects of over tourism with their assistance and organizations, stakeholders, and others can manage this issue.

5. Discussions

This research mainly focusses on the condition of popular city center during the overcrowding and how it affects their quality of life and tourism sphere. Top most visited destinations which came across to over tourism during 2023 around the world. They are followings:

1. Italy (Rome) --- total number of tourist arrivals were equal to 445.3 million during 2023, 35 million tourists in Rome, 2023, 9% over 2022, 32 million.
2. Barcelona --- attracts 9,2 million tourists, while 12 million visitors came to the Catalan.
3. Amsterdam--- 20 million tourists visited (according to the Research & Statistics unit), population equal to 1000 000.
4. Paris--- 36,9 million in 2023.
5. Venice--- 5.5 million in 2023.

- 6. Bali--- 5,273,258 thousand visitors in 2023.
- 7. Athens--- hosted to 7 million tourists in 2023.
- 8. Miami--- 26.5 million visitors in 2022.
- 9. Dubrovnik--- 1,244,159 tourist arrivals, and 3,885,431 overnight stays in 2023.
- 10. Mallorca --- with 12.2 million visitors in 2023.

Italy, Greece and Amsterdam are on of the most top 10 visited countries in the globe. The Dutch metropolis damaged a lot from over tourism in 2019 because the number of travelers were equal 22 million while its total number of populations was equal to 900 000. Most of the countries above try to solve the issue and set some rules and regulations.

For instance, Barcelona started to increase the tourist tax from 2023 due to the tourism congestion. Besides that, from this year Bali also try to increase price of tourist tax. In Venice, tourists group sizes and arrival of large cruise ships limited because of the protection of this historical city.

4 most tourist overcrowded countries Greece, Turkey, Italy and Amsterdam are facing some challenges, because those countries streets, beaches, and attractions are almost covered with people in the spring and summer peak. And now all of those 4 countries started to promote their sustainable tourism, eco-systems, set up some regulations and rules for safety of their country and some of them reduce range of tourism types which can lead to damage the environment such as cruise ships.

And I think it will help them to stabilize the condition of tourism sphere. Mostly European countries hosted many tourists from different part of the world. It will help them to grow the GDP of country, but it can be harmful for cities and residents as well.

This chart shows the number of tourist arrivals all over the world from 1980 to 2030. Europe is always the most visited place, and most of counties which faced

with overcrowded are in Europe as well. Countries of Asia and Pacific in the 2nd place by the total number of tourist arrivals.

6.Recommendations

It is highly recommended that to make a different type of tourism products in these countries help to reduce over tourism in one place. They have to promote country sides' tourism places, attract tourists in a different part of the countries. They have to promote sustainable tourism; they have to support eco-tourism in those countries. Besides that, it is very important to develop the quality of education and training skills of tour operators, employees of tourism industry, inasmuch as it helps to improve the quality of tourism industry.

7. Conclusion

In a conclusion, it is very important to know, and to understand about over-tourism and its impacts on nations' growth. To improve tourism industry is the best choice for increasing the GDP of a country, but it has some disadvantages which might be harmful for environment, for culture, for citizens, and for tourists themselves. For reducing this kind of problems, both visitors and local residents, all stakeholders, communities, organizations and government should try together for solving all problems. Overall, this study highlighted the role of managing tourism in a right way and to promote a responsible travel

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